

On the Diophantine Equation $3^x + 5^y \cdot 19^z = u^2$

Xu Ai-juan¹, Deng Mou-jie^{2*}

¹ College of Information Science and Technology, Hainan University

Haikou 570228, China

Email: xaj1650404852@163.com

² College of Information Science and Technology, Hainan University

Haikou 570228, China

Email: moujie_deng@163.com

Abstract

In this paper, we study the Diophantine equation $3^x + 5^y \cdot 19^z = u^2$. Using elementary methods we show that this Diophantine equation has exactly three solutions (x,y,z,u) , namely: $(1,0,0,2)$, $(4,0,1,10)$ and $(2,2,1,22)$.

Keywords: Exponential Diophantine equation; elementary methods; non-negative integer solutions.

MSC 2010 Classification: 11D61.

1. Introduction

Let a, b be positive integers. The Diophantine equation of type $a^x + b^y = z^2$ have been studied by some authors[1,3,4,6-9]. In 2012, Sroysang.B^[6] showed that the only non-negative integer solution (x,y,z) to the Diophantine equation $3^x + 5^y = z^2$ is $(1,0,2)$. In 2013, Rabago.J.F.T^[3] proved that the only non-negative integer solutions (x,y,z) to the Diophantine equations $3^x + 19^y = z^2$ and $3^x + 91^y = z^2$ are $(1,0,2)$, $(4,1,10)$ and $(1,0,2)$, $(2,1,10)$ respectively. Let a, b, c be positive integers. In this paper, we study a special case of the Diophantine equation of type $a^x + b^y c^z = u^2$. Using elementary methods we show that Diophantine equation $3^x + 5^y 19^z = u^2$ has exactly three non-negative integer solutions (x,y,z,u) , namely: $(1,0,0,2)$, $(4,0,1,10)$ and $(2,2,1,22)$. Note that in the proofs of Theorems in [1] and [6-9], the result of Mihalescu.P^[2] were used, while our proof is elementary.

2. Main result

Theorem 1. *The non-negative integer solutions (x, y, z, u) to the Diophantine equation*

$$3^x + 5^y 19^z = u^2 \quad (2.1)$$

are $(1,0,0,2)$, $(4,0,1,10)$ and $(2,2,1,22)$.

Proof. We consider four cases.

Case 1 $y = z = 0$. In this case we obtain a solution $(x,y,z,u) = (1,0,0,2)$.

* Corresponding author

Case 2 $y = 0$ and $z > 0$. Taking modulo 19 we have $3^x \equiv u^2 \pmod{19}$, which gives

$$(-1)^x = \left(\frac{3}{19}\right)^x = \left(\frac{u}{19}\right)^2 = 1$$

and we thus get $x = 2x_1$. From $u^2 - 3^{2x_1} = 19^z$ we have

$$2 \cdot 3^{x_1} = 19^z - 1. \quad (2.2)$$

We consider two subcases .

Subcase 2.1 $z = 1$. In this subcase we obtain a solution $(x, y, z, u) = (4, 0, 1, 10)$.

Subcase 2.2 $z > 1$. From $19^z - 1 = (19 - 1)(19^{z-1} + 19^{z-2} + \dots + 19 + 1)$ we get

$$(19^{z-1} + 19^{z-2} + \dots + 19 + 1) \equiv 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 + 1 \equiv z \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$$

Let $z = 3z_1$. Since

$$19^z - 1 = (19^3)^{z_1} - 1 = (19^3 - 1) \sum_{i=0}^{z_1-1} (19^3)^i = 2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 127 \sum_{i=0}^{z_1-1} (19^3)^i$$

(2.2) has no solution.

Case 3 $y > 0$ and $z = 0$. In this case (2.1) becomes

$$3^x + 5^y = u^2. \quad (2.3)$$

Similar to the proof of Case 2, we get $x = 2x_1$. From $3^x + 5^y \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $u^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ it follows that (2.3) has no solution.

Case 4 $yz > 0$. In this case we have

$$(u - 3^{x_1})(u + 3^{x_1}) = 5^y \cdot 19^z.$$

We consider three subcases.

Subcase 4.1 $u - 3^{x_1} = 1, u + 3^{x_1} = 5^y 19^z$. In this subcase we have

$$2 \cdot 3^{x_1} = 5^y \cdot 19^z - 1. \quad (2.4)$$

Taking modulo 3, 4, 8 in turn (2.4) gives $y \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, $z \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ respectively. Finally, from $2 \cdot 3^{x_1} \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{5}$, $5^y \cdot 19^z - 1 \equiv -1 \pmod{5}$ it follows that (2.4) has no solution.

Subcase 4.2. $u - 3^{x_1} = 5^y, u + 3^{x_1} = 19^z$. In this subcase we have

$$2 \cdot 3^{x_1} = 19^z - 5^y. \quad (2.5)$$

Similar to the proof of subcase 4.1, taking (2.5) modulo 3, 4, 8, 5 in turn, we deduce that (2.5) has no solution.

Subcase 4.3. $u - 3^{x_1} = 19^z, u + 3^{x_1} = 5^y$. In this subcase we have

$$2 \cdot 3^{x_1} = 5^y - 19^z. \quad (2.6)$$

Taking modulo 3, 4, 8 in turn, (2.6) gives

$$y \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, z \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}.$$

We show that $x_1 = 1$. Suppose $x_1 > 1$. If $y \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$, let

$$x_1 \equiv 1, 3, 5 \pmod{6}, z \equiv 1, 3, 5 \pmod{6},$$

taking modulo 7 (2.6) gives $x_1 \equiv 3 \pmod{6}, z \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. Let $y \equiv 0, 6 \pmod{12}, z \equiv 5, 11 \pmod{12}$. From $2 \cdot 3^{x_1} \equiv 2 \pmod{13}$ and $5^y - 19^z \equiv 1, 3, 10, 12 \pmod{13}$ we deduce that (2.6) has no solution. If $y \equiv 2, 4 \pmod{6}$, then from

$$5^y \equiv 7, 4 \pmod{9}, 19^z \equiv 1 \pmod{9}$$

we get $5^y - 19^z \equiv 6, 3 \pmod{9}$. But $2 \cdot 3^{x_1} \equiv 0 \pmod{9}$, this is a contradiction. Thus $x_1 = 1$, and (2.6) becomes

$$5^y - 19^z = 6. \quad (2.7)$$

Since $5^{6k} \equiv 1 \pmod{9}, 19^z \equiv 1 \pmod{9}$, taking modulo 9 (2.7) gives $y \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$. Then taking modulo 7 (2.7) gives $z \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$. Let

$$y \equiv 2, 8 \pmod{12}, z \equiv 1, 7 \pmod{12}.$$

Since

$$5^y \equiv 12, 1 \pmod{13}, 19^z \equiv 6, 7 \pmod{13}, 5^y - 19^z \equiv 6 \pmod{13},$$

taking (2.7) modulo 13 we obtain $y \equiv 2 \pmod{12}, z \equiv 1 \pmod{12}$.

Let

$$y \equiv 2, 14, 26, 38, 50 \pmod{60}, z \equiv 1, 13, 25, 37, 49 \pmod{60}.$$

Because

$$5^y \equiv 3, 9, 5, 4, 1 \pmod{11}, 19^z \equiv 8, 6, 10, 2, 7 \pmod{11},$$

taking modulo 11 (2.7) gives

$$y \equiv 2 \pmod{60}, z \equiv 1 \pmod{60};$$

or

$$y \equiv 26 \pmod{60}, z \equiv 25 \pmod{60};$$

or

$$y \equiv 50 \pmod{60}, z \equiv 13 \pmod{60}.$$

Taking (2.7) modulo 31 we obtain that $y \equiv 2 \pmod{60}, z \equiv 1 \pmod{60}$. Let

$$y \equiv 2, 62, 122, 182, 242 \pmod{300}, z \equiv 1, 61, 121, 181, 241 \pmod{300}.$$

Because

$$5^y \equiv 25, 92, 80, 52, 54 \pmod{101}, 19^z \equiv 19, 37, 88, 81, 78 \pmod{101},$$

taking (2.7) modulo 101 we obtain that $y \equiv 2 \pmod{300}, z \equiv 1 \pmod{300}$. Suppose $y = 2 + 300k, z = 1 + 300l$.

From $6 = 25 - 19$ and (2.7) we have

$$25(5^{300k} - 1) = 19(19^{300l} - 1).$$

Then from $19^{300l} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{125}$ we get $k = 0$, and thereby $l = 0$. Thus the only solution to (2.7) is $(y, z) = (2, 1)$, which implies that the only positive integer solution to (2.1) is $(2, 2, 1, 22)$. This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Corollary 1. *The only nonnegative integer solution (x, y, z) to the Diophantine equation $3^x + 5^y = z^2$ is $(1, 0, 2)$.*

Corollary 2. *The only non-negative integer solutions (x, y, z) to the Diophantine equations $3^x + 19^y = z^2$ are $(1, 0, 2)$, $(4, 1, 10)$.*

Remark. In 1993, Scott.R^[5] showed that if p is prime, $b > 1$ and c are positive integers, then except for five cases, the Diophantine equations $p^x - b^y = c$ has at most one solution. Using this result we can show that the only solution to (2.7) is $(y, z) = (2, 1)$. But the method used in [5] is not elementary.

Conclusions

In this paper, using elementary method we show that the Diophantine equation has exactly three solutions (x, y, z, u) , namely: $(1, 0, 0, 2)$, $(4, 0, 1, 10)$ and $(2, 2, 1, 22)$. As corollaries, we get the result of Sroysang.B^[6] and part of the results of Rabago.J.F.T^[3].

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